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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Poor asthma control is associated with both biological and psychological factors. Anxiety during asthma attacks causes hyperventilation and related bronchospasm and is often associated with depression (Borra, Cohen, & Busse, 2025). Type D personality consists of two main parts like negative emotionality and social inhibition. Negative emotionality is the tendency to experience negative emotions. Social inhibition is the tendency to be inhibited in expressing these negative emotions (van de Ven, Wittelman, & Tiggeleman, 2013; Witusik et al., 2018). The purpose is to evaluate the relationship between the degree of asthma control and the severity of Type D personality components.

Materials and Methods: 120 people were accepted to the study from the Immunology and Allergy clinic of Isparta City Hospital, in 4 groups (Healthy (n:30), fully controlled asthma (n:30), partially controlled asthma (n:30), uncontrolled asthma group (n:30)). Asthma control test was used for asthma control degree; Beck Depression Inventory was used for depression severity. DS-14 scale was used for type D personality (negative emotionality and social inhibition) and those who scored at least 10 points in both sections were accepted as type D personality.

Results: The mean age was 35.93 ± 9.81 , 36.2 ± 10.55 , 34.9 ± 10.14 , 33.83 ± 8.55 in the healthy, fully controlled asthma, partially controlled asthma, and poorly controlled asthma groups, respectively, and were similar ($p=0.83$). Beck depression scale score (7.5 ± 2.30 , 8 ± 2.01 , 9.33 ± 1.62 , 13.23 ± 2.55 , $p=0.000$), negative emotionality score (7.73 ± 2.54 , 8 ± 3 , 8.83 ± 2.71 , 11.63 ± 3.51 , $p=0.000$), social inhibition score (8.93 ± 3.11 , 9.13 ± 2.17 , 8.8 ± 2.56 , 11 ± 3.15 , $p=0.023$; healthy, fully controlled asthma, partially controlled asthma, poorly controlled asthma groups, respectively) were higher in the uncontrolled asthma group than in the other groups. Beck depression inventory was positively correlated with negative emotionality, social inhibition and total score ($r=0.644$, $p=0.000$; $r=0.471$, $p=0.006$; $r=0.612$, $p=0.000$, respectively). The risk of type D personality was higher in the poorly controlled asthma group than in the healthy group (OR=3.33; 95% CI: 0.99-11.13), partially controlled asthma group (OR=4.33; 95% CI: 1.20-15.60), and fully controlled asthma group (OR=9.33; 95% CI: 1.86-46.68) ($p<0.05$). The percentage of type D personality in the poorly controlled asthma group was 40%, significantly higher than the other groups ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion: Depression severity, negative emotionality score, social inhibition score and type D personality percentage were greater in the poorly controlled asthma group than in the other groups. Type D personality may be both a cause and a consequence of poorly controlled asthma.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Asthma control, depressiveness, negative emotionality, social inhibition.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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